

**SCHOOL EDUCATION AND NEO-LIBERALISM WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO GEOGRAPHY CURRICULUM:
A THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE**

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ABSTRACT

India's economic reform in 1991, globalization, and privatization affect the education system. Neoliberal thinkers support a market having free economy, which describes the establishment of private organizations. These private institutions have the freedom to establish market prices whatever they want. Neo-liberalism supports a laissez-faire economy and short intervention by the government. It deals with increasing the effect of privatization and decreasing the effect of direct government involvement. The efficiency of market competition receives significant emphasis. The researcher wants to see the history of school education in West Bengal and also teaching-learning strategies for geography classes in the schools. The researcher purposively selected the three districts in West Bengal. The current study's technique is grounded in qualitative research. To collect primary and secondary sources of data, the researcher used a historical research design for this study. It finds that after 1991's economic reform, private educational institutions have continuously grown. Private schools maintain the qualities that help to strengthen students' content knowledge more than that of government schools.

Keywords: Globalization, Geography Curriculum, School Education, Neo-liberalism

INTRODUCTION

Neo-liberalism means a free market capitalism policy. Where every individual has the freedom to establish market focus upon privatization and global trends. For education purpose, neoliberalism deals with the establishment of private institutions with respect to globalization. After 199, India's reform, globalization, and privatization affected the education system. Neoliberal thinkers support a market having free economy, which describes the establishment of private

organizations. These private institutions have the freedom to establish market prices whatever they want. Neo-liberalism supports a laissez-faire economy and short intervention by the government. Neoliberalism deals with increasing the effect of privatization and decreasing the effect of direct government involvement. It is greatly emphasized on the efficiency of the market competition. In India, the government provides financial support for the school education system, but in the era of globalization and technology-oriented education system, many private schools have grown up. Globalization also discusses the quality education and skill-based education system with the basis of curriculum innovation. The term globalization is also frequently used in geography. It is used to describe how trade and information technology have made the entire world into a connected and interdependent place. In the geography curriculum, economic, social, regional, and so on portions are there; these all reflect upon globalization, and private institutions provide quality and skill-based education to the learners.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE STUDY

- a) Banerjee (2006) had conducted a study on “Geography education in Indian schools”. The aim of the study was to see the development and to investigate the dynamics and practicality of geography as a subject that is taught in the schools. Research focused on some thought that was a geography textbook written by an Indian or regional geographer, not as much quality as the foreign author. Women were getting more interested in admission in geography than men. But in the post-1991s, Indian men were also interestingly attracted to geography with the revolution of IT sectors, GIS, etc., for getting jobs. Geography curriculum is examined, and global issues are incorporated into it.
- b) Alam (2010) had conducted his study on “Recent trends in school geography in India”. The aim of this study was to see the trends of geography in Indian schools with the help of NCFSE and NCF. This research was fully based upon a qualitative study that had focused on secondary data. The result showed that NCERT had focused upon students’ geographical skills and knowledge. Integration of geography under social science may have a negative effect on the quality of geography in the school curriculum. Geography should reflect some of the major issues about the world; it will make the students aware of the world. At the end, both the policies had ignored ‘world geography’ and its implications in terms of developing an international perspective among schoolchildren. Geography curriculum should be included with world geography so that students could know about the world and different territorial knowledge, particularly in the field of globalization.
- c) Butt (2011) had conducted his study on “Globalization, geography education and the curriculum: what are the challenges for curriculum makers in geography?”. The objective of the study was to see the challenges for curriculum makers in geography education. This study was analytical and qualitative in nature. In the conclusion, results showed that geography curriculum makers faced the challenges of seeking to conceptualize globalization and the present opportunities for curriculum makers in geography and

beyond. Creating a conflict between globalization and global capitalism. If schools explore themes related to globalization, they will have to face challenges, but it will be helpful for their lifelong learning. Another thing was globalization should not be the main focus area in the part of the geography curriculum.

- d) Mondal & Basak (2017) had conducted their study on “Private vs. Public school in the present scenario of basic education—a case study of Barasat Municipality, North 24 Parganas”. The objective of this study was to evaluate the comparison between public and private schools at the basic education stage in Barasat. The researcher used qualitative research methodology for conducting the study. The result showed that infrastructure, quality of education, and quantities of teaching staff are poorer in public schools than in private schools, and it had accelerated mushroom growth of primary schools.
- e) Singh (2020) had conducted his study on “Geographic education in Indian schools: development, trends and issues”. The aim of this study was to track down the evolutionary history of geographic education in India at the school level. The researcher had conducted this study with a descriptive analytical view. At the conclusion, it was seen that geography and geographical awareness were very well developed in ancient India. Geography is facing a crisis of survival in India. That’s why the future of Indian geography is not so bright. It needs some positive redesign.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Given the prevailing global worldview of neo-liberalism, which emphasizes individual responsibility, market-driven policies, privatization, and deregulation, the necessity and usefulness of geography curricula in schools assume new significance. Critical thinking about the global system and understanding of issues like urbanization, migration, and climate change—all of which are frequently depoliticized in neoliberal discourse—are fostered by geography education. Other factors include the ongoing expansion of private schools, the provision of teaching-learning strategies, and the impact of global challenges on the educational system of both public and private educational institutions. The provision of a skill-based education system is also essential. Therefore, in light of neo-liberalism, it is thought important to carry out a study on the geography curriculum in schools.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To know the history of neo-liberalism in school education.
2. To know about the teaching-learning strategy of geography classrooms in the schools in the light of neo-liberalism.

METHODOLOGY

The approach of the current study is grounded in qualitative research, which includes the historical research technique with primary data sources (reports from the Indian government

about school education) and secondary data sources (books, journals, websites, etc.). Analysis of objective 1 is delimited to West Bengal only.

NEO-LIBERALISM AND EDUCATION POLICY

In the neo-liberal era, education is constantly evolving. By privatizing as many government functions as possible, including education, neo-liberals hope to reduce the size of the state. Furthermore, companies, non-profit groups, and philanthropic organizations have a greater influence on policymaking since the government's role is diminished and local control is weakened. Last but not least, the outdated bureaucratic structures that are thought to be too sluggish to react to market forces are to be replaced by market-based institutions in education and other government agencies. Neoliberals aim to privatize things like transportation, healthcare, and education. Education has been radically changed under the ascendancy of neoliberal ideologies. The emphasis on markets affects how government's role is conceived and policy is developed. By privatizing as many government functions as possible, including education, neo-liberals hope to reduce the size of the state. Furthermore, companies, non-profit groups, and philanthropic organizations have a greater influence on policymaking as a result of the diminished role of government and the erosion of local control. Last but not least, market-based institutions are to replace government agencies and educational institutions. Furthermore, the new public management replaces the outdated bureaucratic structures that are thought to be too slow to react to market forces, changing the way schools are run. With the help of standardized tests and other quantitative metrics, new public administration places more importance on output and performance than on inputs and procedures, such as funding and standards. "Governance through numbers" refers to the use of standardized tests to hold teachers and students accountable. Neoliberals also aim to replace bureaucratic, hierarchical administration with governance, which is the power of adaptable, diverse networks. It is now easier for the wealthy and well-connected to influence and profit from the decision-making process because of the rise of networks and the replacement of hierarchical public policy-making with hierarchical and frequently private policy-making. Additionally, decision-making has shifted from local and provincial levels to national and international levels (Ball and Junemann, 2012).

EFFECT ON NEO-LIBERALISM ON INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

In 1994, India ratified the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS), which was part of the World Trade Organization (WTO), entered in 1995. The World Trade Organization's policy recommendations opposed using public funds to expand higher education. Due to financial limitations imposed on state governments by several neoliberal fiscal "reforms" and fiscal concessions to capitalists, the quality of public institutions has begun to decline. Universities are supposed to provide the world market with skilled labour. It should come as no surprise that the deplorable condition of public higher education has caused private institutions to proliferate (Patnaik, 2007). Higher education, according to the World Bank's report "Higher Education: Lessons of Experience," is a private and quasi-private product that enables students to demand a larger market for their abilities. These are private profit-making organizations that are in the business of teaching in order to make money, not private charity organizations that have

operated with some degree of independence from the government. The neoliberal shift in higher education was aided by the Private Universities Act of 1995. A notable example of how private capital has increased its participation in higher education is the rise in deemed universities, the opening of private universities, and the resulting rise in enrolment in these establishments. Subsidies for higher education were subsequently cut in 1997. It was suggested that subsidies be reduced from 90% to 25% over a five-year period. The Ambani-Birla Report from 2000, which suggested that the subsidized system be completely retracted by 2015, supported this plan. Aside from the push to raise an increasing amount of funds from non-state actors, privatization is flourished at various levels, even within universities, such as through the contractualization of the teaching and non-teaching staff. Here, the intelligentsia's role becomes important. They develop into important tools that foster agreement in support of areas. It will be necessary to usurp the role of intellectuals and everyone who is eager to keep higher education a place where independent and critical thought can flourish.

GLOBALIZATION AND CURRICULUM CHANGE

Continuous educational changes are happening due to the direct effect of globalization. The blurring of geographic borders to embrace diversity in educational practices, resources, and culture in order to take advantage of the global educational treasure trove is known as globalization in education. India's international boarding schools support global education by giving students access to the greatest staff members and an extensive, limitless library of learning materials. In order to eliminate regional barriers to education and unite cultures, races, faiths, and traditions from throughout the world, schools accept international exchange students. By teaching them about current events, global concerns, and issues, students are ready to become global citizens and learn from their peers. Let's study more about how globalization affects education.

(Source: Turk & Atasoy, 2020, p: 70)

Figure 1: Global Awareness in Education

For students to remain educated and establish their own opinions in the present period, they must be exposed to the social, economic, political, and cultural agendas on a global scale. Additionally, it fosters a sense of community rather than loneliness. To make wise decisions, it is essential to have a global perspective. The organization of contents must use the ‘Thematic approach’, which means contents under curriculum construction must be from local to regional and from national to global context (NCFSE, 2023). According to NCFSE 2023, curriculum must contain-

(Source: NCFSE: 2023)

Figure 2: Curriculum Construction based on NCFSE: 2023

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Objective 1: To know the history of neo-liberalism in school education

An essential component of any generation’s development is education. Free market capitalism is a component of neo-liberalism. This strategy entails integrating private organizations into society. Compared to government educational institutions, private colleges offer top-notch educational facilities at higher profit margins through tuition increases. Talk primarily about school education. West Bengal was a major contributor to the creation of India’s current educational system. West Bengal introduced Western educational models to India. William Carey, Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar, Raja Ram Mohan Roy. David Hare were instrumental in the successful founding of contemporary schools in West Bengal. The data was gathered by the researcher from the aforementioned three West Bengal districts: Howrah, Birbhum, and Kolkata. The researcher selected three districts in West Bengal’s government and private secondary and upper secondary schools for this topic. These are Birbhum, Kolkata, and Howrah. For this purpose, data is gathered from government-affiliated secondary and higher secondary schools as well as private institutions between 1900 and 2020, or before and after independence.

(Source: Sengupta & Divyaganananda, 2020)

Figure 3 : All public and private schools in three West Bengal districts

In conclusion, it is evident from the aforementioned research that, in comparison to Howrah and Birbhum, Kolkata has the most government and private secondary and upper secondary schools out of the three districts. The bar graph above further demonstrates how advanced private institutions are in the districts of Kolkata and Howrah, with the majority of private schools emerging as a result of the Indian economic reforms of 1991. Numerous studies have demonstrated that, in comparison to government schools, private schools offer higher-quality education, and many members of the middle and upper classes wish to demonstrate their social standing by enrolling their kids in private schools. Data also showed that, due to economic status, private school education—primarily secondary and higher secondary—is expanding more quickly in Kolkata and Howrah than in Birbhum. The districts of Birbhum are undoubtedly in worse financial shape than Kolkata and Howrah. Following India's economic reforms in 1991, West Bengal and India both saw the full impact of neo-liberalism. Consequently, private educational institutions entered the market with the intention of making as much money as possible while still offering high-quality instruction.

Objective 2: To know about the teaching-learning strategy of geography classrooms in the schools in the light of neo-liberalism.

Teaching-learning techniques or strategies are most important while engaged in a subject curriculum. Child-centred pedagogy, as defined by NCF-2005, prioritizes children's experiences, voices, and active engagement. According to this strategy, geography teaching and learning strategies should be centred on assisting students in gaining information and skills in a dynamic setting. It is crucial that the process of learning encourages both teachers and students to be creative and inquisitive. Geography instruction has to embrace approaches that foster critical thinking, creativity, and aesthetics. As a key facilitator of curriculum implementation, the geography teacher must clarify ideas in a way that students can understand and work to make learning

more interactive by moving beyond merely teaching facts to include students in debate and discussion. The main objective of the NCFSE 2000 was to reduce the study pressure on the school children (Singh, 2020). Curriculum load is very harmful for school students. Students learning based on investigation in the field are also an important part of the students' cognitive development (Aliman et al., 2019). According to NEP 2020, the main focus goes on students' skill development and strengthening students' constructive knowledge. Both government and private educational institutions should provide less emphasis on input but greater emphasis on learning outcomes and also reduce the curriculum content to enhance essential learning and critical thinking.

Table 1 : Constructive students' improving learning outcome

Factors	Impact upon students' learning
Subject Knowledge	Teachers with their subject knowledge and understanding should focus on students' learning. They should think about how students learn the contents very precisely and also should identify the learners learning drawbacks from the topics.
Quality teaching instruction	Proper questioning and the use of proper assessment by the subject teachers are also important for the students' quality learning through providing clues and extra time to solve the problems.
Climate of the classroom	The interaction between students and teachers should be of high quality.
Classroom management	The effective use of learning time and good quality of school managing behaviour

(Source: Coe et al., 2014)

Some key teaching-learning strategies for geography classes are given below :

1. Interactive maps and globes-Use physical maps and digital maps for students' spatial awareness, which visualize locations and regions.
2. Excursion-Visit to the geographical places (river, mountain, plain land areas, etc.) to provide real-world learning experiences.
3. Project-based learning- Encourage the geography students to participate in the project by instructing them to develop a model, presentation, or research- related project to strengthen the content knowledge.
4. Uses of technology Use of technology in terms of uses of projectors, digital print materials is also helpful to students, which helps them to acquire constructive knowledge.

5. Case studies and current information provide knowledge about real-world geographical events like earthquakes, floods and deforestation to connect theoretical knowledge to practical application.
6. Group discussion and debates-organize inter and intra quiz, debate competitions to help the students to acquire information beyond the syllabus. Group discussion also strengthens student concepts about the subject.

Private schools provide much more qualitative teaching–learning strategies in terms of technology assistance, projects/ assignments, extracurricular activities for students’ learning than government schools.

CONCLUSION

In India, school geography was first taught using a disciplinary colonial framework. Like everywhere else, particularly in Europe, its content was heavily influenced by regional and physical landscape. Following the nation’s independence, goals were reassessed, and educational practices changed over time. Only when geography is taught so that the components of the social and physical sciences are examined within the regional framework can the subject’s true educational value be realized. Global processes may impact local events, while local events may influence global processes in the age of globalization. In West Bengal, private schools are growing up here and there. After 1991’s economic reforms in India, private educational institutions have continuously grown. Private schools maintain the qualities that help to strengthen students’ content knowledge. Due to high in-school fees, many people cannot afford this. So, the government should take initiatives for updating government school teachers teaching abilities through organized workshops, seminars, etc.

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